

The Church of St. Paraskevi, Kitiros, Crete

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Entry tags: Crete, Greek Orthodox, Greece, Byzantine, Orthodoxy, Church, Orthodoxy, Christian Traditions, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Monument, Religious Place, Religious Group

The Church of St. Paraskevi is a single nave chapel covered with a pointed barrel vault and a saddle roof on the exterior. A small cemetery surrounds the western end of the church now enclosed by a modern fence. Located just east of the small village of Kitiros in the southwest corner of Crete, the church sits on a high outcrop overlooking the small river Pelekaniotikos which runs down to the coastal town of Palaiochora, roughly 15km away by foot. The dedicatory inscription of the church, partially preserved along the southwest wall above the image of the Archangel Michael, indicates that the church was built and painted with the contribution and efforts of the Christians of the district (τούρμα) of Kitiros, which includes the various small villages in the surrounding area including Chasi, Sklavopoula, and the metochi of Moustaki in the year 6881, Indiction 15 (1372-73). Inside the church, a transverse arch divides the interior into two bays with the sanctuary separated today by a wooden iconostasis. The wall paintings, although damaged in places, are in good condition. The conch of the sanctuary shows the Virgin Blachernitissa above four co-officiating Bishops flanked on either side by St. Stephen and St. Romanus the Melodist. The lower register of both the north and south walls of the sanctuary are decorated with ten frontal saints including the monk St. John Kalybites, St. Simeon Stylites and St. Anthony. The barrel vault is decorated with the Ascension of Christ to the east and, to the west, four compartments showing the Anastasis, the Empty Sepulchre, the Incredulity of Thomas, and Christ Appearing to the Two Marys. The raised transverse arch in the center of the church is decorated with the prophets David and Jeremiah to the north and Solomon and Isaiah to the south. The images of St. Peter and St. Paul face one another along the lower register of the archway. On the southern wall, a large Deesis, showing Christ flanked by the Virgin Mary and St. John the Baptist, is followed by the images of St. Kyriaki and St. Marina. The northern wall similarly shows St. Paraksevi, presented frontally under an archway decorated with palm fronds, followed by the images of St. George on horseback and St. Mamas. Scenes from the life of St. Paraskevi, the titular saint, along with images from the Christological Cycle decorate the barrel vault. To the right of the entrance, below a large image of the Crucifixion, are scenes of Hell and the damned including images of The Farmer who Ploughs and Reaps over the Boundary Line, the Thieving Tailor, The Miller Who Cheats at the Scales, and the Livestock Thief and Robber (shown with an ass on his back and a goat hanging from his neck). The larger agricultural concerns of the communities who sponsored this church can be seen in the choice of Individual Sinners. The inclusion of both St. Mamas and St. George, important saints for both shepherds and farmers alike, shows the need to protect livestock from illness and theft. Additionally, the two female sinners, one punished for not nursing her child and the other for sexual license, demonstrates both the anxiety concerning the wellbeing of children and the larger social and moral boundaries set within these communities. Although the Church of St. Paraskevi is most famous for its image of the Individual Sinners, the extensive cycle of the Life of St. Paraskevi is also important for the iconographic diversions from what is seen in other preserved cycles of the saint.

Date Range: 1372 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Kitiros, Chania (Selino), Crete

Region tags: Greece, Crete

The village of Kitiros is located in the southwest corner of Crete in the province of Selino (Chania) overlooking the small river Pelekaniotikos.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: The Byzantine church is surrounded by a modern cemetery.

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Single nave chapel with a pointed barrel vault interior and a saddle roof exterior

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

–Other [specify]: Worship and burial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: St. Paraskevi

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Spatharakis, Ioannis. *Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete*. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. See no. 41, 116-18 (with earlier bibliography)

– Source 2: Lymberopoulou, Angeliki, ed. *Hell in the Byzantine World: A History of Art and Religion in Venetian Crete and the Eastern Mediterranean*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020. See no. 21

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Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Other [specify]: Built by the communities of the district of Kitiros including the villages of Kitiros, Chasi, Rogozo, Agios Konstantinos, Sklavopoula, Kalami, and the metochi of Moustaki.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

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Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

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Is the place situated in a rural setting:

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Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: The Byzantine church is surrounded by a modern cemetery.

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Single nave chapel with a pointed barrel vault interior and a saddle roof exterior

↳ One single feature

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↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

–Other [specify]: Worship and burial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

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↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: St. Paraskevi

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

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↳ Groups:

– Other [specify]: Built by the communities of the district of Kitiros including the villages of Kitiros, Chasi, Rogozo, Agios Konstantinos, Sklavopoula, Kalami, and the metochi of Moustaki.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

Notes: The church has been whitewashed on the exterior.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Extensive wall paintings.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: There is a modern wooden iconostasis separating the sanctuary.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The wall paintings include images of Christ in the Deesis and in the Christological cycles.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The wall paintings include standing figures of saints, monks, and prophets. It also includes scenes from the life of the titular saint, St. Paraskevi.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The wall paintings include images of individual sinners along with people associated with the life of Christ and the life of St. Paraskevi.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Dedicatory inscription on the west wall of the church.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Icons are included in the wooden iconostasis.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The painting cycle reflects standard iconography of the Orthodox Christian faith.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Beyond the dedicatory inscription, there are inscriptions identifying the figures (including both the saints and the individual sinners). There are also titles on many of the narrative scenes.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: There is a formal dedicatory inscription on the west wall of the church above the image of the Archangel Michael.

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: Scenes of Hell on the west wall.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Including images of the apostles and saints.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from both the Christological Cycle and from the Life of St. Paraskevi.

↳ Human narratives

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– I don't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Plaster, brick and stone.

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

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Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– No
Notes: The church has been whitewashed on the exterior.

↳ On the inside:
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Notes: Extensive wall paintings.

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Notes: There is a modern wooden iconostasis separating the sanctuary.

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– Yes

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↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Including images of the apostles and saints.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from both the Christological Cycle and from the Life of St. Paraskevi.

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: A contemporary cemetery surrounds the church.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
– I don't know

Are formal burials present:
– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:
– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:
– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):
– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:
– Yes
Notes: A contemporary cemetery surrounds the church.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:
– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:
– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:
Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.
– No

Are grave goods present:
– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– I don't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

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